

A Comparative Study of Resilience in Gender Differences among Adolescents Girls and Boys

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Abstract:

This intervention program is designed to develop resilience in adolescents because mental health disorders are thought to affect one in seven (14%) of children aged 10 to 19 worldwide, although they are commonly ignored and untreated. This research investigated possible gender disparities in results and assessed the efficacy of a school-based intervention program intended to improve resilience in adolescents. This study used a quasi-experimental research design. A total sample of 50 adolescents (25 girls + 25 boys) of 7th to 10th standard of two schools of the Etah district of Uttar Pradesh State, were selected by random sampling. In this study, an intervention program was developed targeting 5 skills: Acceptance, Empathy, Decision Making, Effective Communication, and Self-Awareness. Activities based on these skills were conducted by the researcher in the normal class schedule. Unpaired t-tests were performed to examine differences in resilience related skills between adolescent boys and girls. The results indicated that no statistically significant differences between boys and girls on each of the measured skills (all $p > 0.05$). All these findings imply that girls and boys equally benefited from the activities with equal development in all five skill areas. The conclusion is that "gender" is not a factor influencing resilience among adolescents. Both girls and boys seem to equally benefit from activities aimed at building resilience, indicative of a well-balanced development of interpersonal and coping abilities. Findings also suggest that resilience-building interventions can be successfully implemented in school settings for both genders.

Keywords: Resilience, Adolescents, Intervention Program, Acceptance, Empathy, Decision-Making, and Self-Awareness

1. Introduction:

Over the past ten years, the prevalence of adolescent mental health disorders has increased, adding to the worldwide health burden. Mental health disorders are thought to affect one in seven (14%) of children aged 10 to 19 worldwide, although they are commonly ignored and untreated (WHO, 2024). Adolescence is a crucial time for psychological and emotional growth, and difficulties like relationships with family members, peer pressure, identity formation, and educational stress frequently characterize it. Adolescents may be more susceptible to mental health issues as a result of physical, emotional, and social changes, such as being exposed to poverty, abuse, or violence. Disruptions to the family system, peer conflicts, the educational setting, sociocultural barriers, physical health vulnerabilities, and a multitasking culture with high standards for success, achievement, and competition can all lead to mental health problems. Unpleasant situations that fail to meet expectations can cause tension or pressure in an individual. Without question, it is impossible to avoid difficult situations when they arise. These issues are particularly significant to the adolescent population. Both retrospective and prospective investigations have demonstrated that the majority of adult psychiatric illnesses start in childhood and adolescence (Copeland et al., 2011; Kessler et al., 2005; Kessler et al., 2007; Kim-Cohen et al., 2003), numerous studies have revealed an alarming frequency of behavior disorders, anxiety, and depression in young people (Costello et al., 2003; Merikangas et al., 2009). Adolescents who suffer from mental health disorders may experience long-term effects on themselves, their families, and the community. During childhood and adolescence, mental illness among young populations can be prevented by providing interventions. Resilience helps individuals better handle stress, adversity, and emotional difficulties, and it can be important in preventing mental illness.

Resilience is best described as "bounce-back ability." It is the ability to overcome obstacles, adapt to life's disappointments, and cope with the daily pressures of daily living. Developing resilience is essential for conquering life's challenges and setbacks. An individual can develop the resilience needed to overcome adversity and thrive in the face of challenges by using these strategies in their life. Resilience is the ability to bounce back and respond positively in the face of significant setbacks, high demands, and extremely stressful circumstances (Kallianta et al., 2021). Although psychologists have long studied resilience, the current focus is on building resilience before experiencing a traumatic or stressful event (Everly Jr et al., 2008).

1.1. Acceptance: Acceptance involves acknowledging the reality of one's thoughts and emotions without resistance. It entails surrendering to what is, allowing oneself to experience feelings as they are, since avoidance only prolongs their presence.

1.2. Empathy: The ability to imagine what it would be like to be in another person's shoes and share that person's thoughts or experiences is known as empathy (Uttamchandani, 2022).

1.3. Decision Making: The capacity to weigh possibilities and make decisions based on knowledge and personal values is referred to as decision-making abilities. These abilities are essential during adolescence as people negotiate social pressures, balance advantages and disadvantages, and think through the possible outcomes of their choices. Young people with strong decision-making abilities can overcome peer pressure and make decisions that are consistent with their values and objectives.

1.4. Effective Communication: The term "effective communication" describes the capacity to listen intently, communicate ideas and emotions clearly, and interpret nonverbal clues. These abilities include listening, empathy, verbal and nonverbal communication, and the ability to adapt one's message to the situation and audience. These abilities are essential for fostering personal development, settling disputes, and creating wholesome relationships.

1.5. Self-awareness: Self-awareness is defined as "the capacity to comprehend one's feelings, ideas, and values and how they impact behavior in various contexts".

Building resilience requires a variety of interrelated abilities, including self-awareness, decision-making, acceptance, empathy, and effective communication. Acceptance lays the groundwork for emotional strength by enabling people to digest their feelings and face reality without resistance. Social support and deep connections are fostered by empathy and are crucial in trying times. Making decisions gives people a sense of control by empowering them to respond to hardship with deliberate, morally motivated decisions. Effective communication promotes emotional stability by allowing people to express their needs, settle problems, and maintain healthy relationships. These abilities are connected by self-awareness, which enables people to better handle stress by understanding their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Together, these abilities enable people to adjust, bounce back, and thrive when faced with life's obstacles, thereby increasing their resilience.

2. Literature review:

Many possible predictors of resilience in adolescents have been identified by recent research. According to Wang et al., (2024) social connection is essential for promoting adolescents' mental health, and empathy is closely related to emotional resilience. Similarly, Vinayak and Judge (2018) demonstrated that empathy and resilience work together to predict adolescents' psychological well-being. According to Loke and Mohd-Zaharim (2019), decision-making mediates the link between risky behaviours and resilience, suggesting that early decision-making skill instruction may minimise adverse consequences. Hwei (2017) found that resilience was substantially predicted by acceptance, forgiveness, and appreciation at the higher education level, highlighting the significance of good psychological traits across age groups.

In addition to factors that predict, several interventions have been shown to improve resilience. Xing et al., (2023) discovered that while psychology course training boosted resilience in younger students during the pandemic, it did not affect older adolescents, indicating the necessity for age-sensitive strategies. While Tripa et al., (2020) showed that school-based group counselling decreased loneliness, improved self-control, and increased resilience among children left behind, Ebrahimi et al., (2022) indicated that acceptance and commitment therapy boosted resilience and self-concept in children with cancer. These results collectively demonstrate that structured programs and treatment approaches can foster resilience, while their efficacy may differ depending on the age, situation, and needs of each individual.

Overall, the research under evaluation shows that both internal strengths like empathy, judgement, and acceptance and external supports like therapy, counselling, and organised intervention programs have an impact on adolescents' resilience. Although these results support the idea that resilience can be fostered through focused tactics, the fact that different age groups and situations respond differently to these strategies indicates that more research is necessary. Very little research, nevertheless, has looked at the differences in adolescent resilience between boys and girls. The majority of the research that is currently available concentrates on broad

adolescent groups without specifically examining gender-based variations. This leaves a gap in our knowledge of whether gender-specific approaches are required or if therapies have the same effect on adolescent boys and girls. This study compares the resilience development of adolescent girls and boys using an intervention program in order to close this difference.

3. Objectives of this study:

1. To develop resilience through an intervention program
2. To compare the level of resilience in girls and boys on completion of the intervention program.

4. Methodology:

4.1. Research Design and Locale of the Study- A quasi-experimental methodology was used in this study to assess the intervention's efficacy. Although the design provided for a fair comparison across groups, it was chosen because random student selection was not feasible in a classroom context. Two schools in Uttar Pradesh's Etah District were selected for the study based on their accessibility and participation availability. Comparability was ensured by the fact that both schools had students in the necessary age range, as well as their teaching techniques. Both boys and girls were included in the study, and their participation and answers were given the same importance. By including both sexes, the results may show a fairer evaluation of the intervention's effectiveness. The activities were executed successfully in actual classroom settings due to the assistance of teachers and school administrators. Therefore, the Etah schools that were chosen offered a fitting and significant environment for examining the program's efficacy.

4.2. Sample Size- In this study, a total of 50 adolescents (25 girls and 25 boys) from classes 7th -10th were selected by random sampling using the chit-jar method. In this method, each person was given a "chit" or slip of paper marked "yes" and "no" and placed in a jar. After that, each student selected a chit at random from the jar. A student who selects a "yes" chit means included in the research work, while a student who selects "no" chit means not included in the research work. This method guarantees that every person in the population has the same opportunity to be chosen. It reduces selection bias and supports valid conclusions about the whole group.

4.3. Tools:

4.3.1. Self-constructed Feedback proforma- A structured feedback proforma was created to assess each skill-based activity's effectiveness. After each activity was over, this self-made form was given out right away. The purpose of this feedback form was to assess the participants' opinions, attitudes and feelings about the activities of each skill so that the effects on their engagement and learning could be systematically evaluated. This feedback consisted of 6 questions. The first five questions use a five-point Likert scale to evaluate the answers. Where a score of four was awarded for "Yes, very much," three for "Somewhat," two for "Neutral," one for "Not really," and zero for "Not at all." This made it easier to determine the student's feelings towards each question. In the last question of each activity's feedback form, participants were asked which activity they enjoyed the most. Four possible answers were offered for this reason, allowing students to choose the one they liked best.

4.3.2. An Intervention Program- Intervention programs are important for building resilience in adolescents. They offer structured chances to develop emotional, social, and cognitive skills that help young people deal with challenges. Intervention programs help by teaching adolescents how to handle emotions, solve problems, set goals, and form healthy relationships.

They also strengthen support systems by including families, schools, and peer groups, creating a safe and caring environment for growth. By promoting self-awareness, acceptance, empathy, decision-making, and effective communication, intervention programs build a foundation for lasting resilience and adaptability in tough times.

In this intervention program, the researcher selected some activities for developing resilience through self-awareness, acceptance, empathy, decision-making, and effective communication skills. The researcher will concentrate on developing resilience through these activities.

This program included activities, interactive worksheets, and discussions to make learning interesting and hands-on. Every activity was created to not only impart knowledge but also provide students with hands-on experience using these abilities in real life situations. While group-based activities fostered cooperation and peer learning, worksheets were offered to stimulate self-reflection.

Participants were given the feedback form at the conclusion of each activity. This made it possible for the researcher to get quick feedback on how relevant, engaging, and helpful each activity was. Through the integration of activities and feedback, the program guaranteed an ongoing cycle of learning, introspection, and development.

Activities included in this intervention- Activities in the intervention program were selected to help participants improve five skills that contribute to developing resilience. Activities like “Self-Esteem Dice” and “Puzzle Pieces of Our” were used to create a better understanding of themselves and recognize their individual characteristics, which in turn helped them improve acceptance skills. Activities like “Story in a Bag” and “Walk in My Shoes” were used to develop empathy skills, which allowed participants to develop compassion and see things from other people's points of view as well. Activities like “the Marshmallow Spaghetti Tower” and “the Decision-Making Wheel” were used to develop decision-making abilities, so the students can weigh their alternatives, consider potential outcomes, and make well-informed decisions. Activities such as “Dumb Charade” and “Broken Telephone” focused on clarity, active listening, and concept expression to improve effective communication skills. Activities such as “My Strength and My Weakness” and “Goal Identification” are used to develop self-awareness that enables participants to evaluate their own strengths, establish goals, and gain confidence.

4.4. Procedure- Two schools in the Etah district of Uttar Pradesh were the locations for this study. A total of 50 adolescents from grades 7 to 10 were selected using the chit-jar random selection method, consisting of 25 girls and 25 boys. After that, the intervention program was put into action, emphasizing five skills: decision-making, empathy, acceptance, self-awareness, and effective communication. Worksheets and interactive activities were used in the normal classroom for each activity. Following each session, students completed a feedback form with a five-point Likert scale and a last question on the activity they enjoyed the most. Frequency, percentage, and the unpaired t-test were used to compare the responses of boys and girls in the data collection process.

4.5. Statistical Analysis- In this study, frequency and percentage were used to analyze the distribution of participants' responses and to compare the difference between boys and girls; the unpaired t-test was used. It was feasible to evaluate if any gender-based differences were significant and to properly present the results by using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

5. Results:

Adolescents' opinions on five skills- acceptance, empathy, decision-making, effective communication, and self-awareness were gathered to assess the efficacy of the intervention. Percentages were used to examine the feedback form replies in order to determine general trends in participation, perceived utility, and future participation willingness. To give a clear image of the experiences of the participants, the percentage distributions are displayed using tables and figures. Additionally, an unpaired t-test was used independently for each skill area to determine whether there were any gender-based differences that were significant. The mean scores, standard deviations, degrees of freedom, t-values, and p-values are presented in a tabular format for the comparisons between boys and girls. In addition to highlighting the activities' overall efficacy, this dual technique of descriptive and inferential research also reveals potential gender variations in how adolescents viewed and profited from them.

Table 1: Responses of the feedback form of Acceptance Skill activities

Questions	Gender	Level of response (%)				
		Yes, very much	Somewhat	Neutral	Not really	Not, at all
activities were engaging and interesting	Girls	68	32	0	0	0
	Boys	76	16	8	0	0
activities helped in self-acceptance	Girls	76	8	16	0	0
	Boys	48	28	24	0	0
activities enhanced creativity	Girls	80	16	4	0	0
	Boys	56	32	12	0	0
wanted to participate in the future	Girls	68	16	12	4	0
	Boys	60	12	24	0	4

In table 1, for the statement “activities were engaging and interesting”, 68% girls and 76% boys strongly agreed that activities that were conducted for developing acceptance skills are engaging and interesting, while 32% girls and 16% boys were little agree. Additionally, 8% of boys expressed a neutral response, which means they neither fully agreed nor fully disagreed.

Regarding the statement that “activities helped in self-acceptance”, 76% girls and 48% boys strongly agreed that acceptance activities help them in developing acceptance skills. In addition, 8% girls and 28% boys somewhat agree with the statement. Moreover, 16% girls and 24% boys reported neutral responses, indicating neither fully agreed nor fully disagreed with the statement.

On the item “activities enhanced creativity”, 80% girls and 56% boys strongly agreed that acceptance activities help in enhancing creativity. Meanwhile, 16% girls and 32% boys responded somewhat, meaning partial agreement with the statement. Furthermore, 4% girls and 12% boys responded neutral, indicating neither fully agreed nor fully disagreed with the statement.

Finally, the statement of willingness “to participate in the future”, 68% girls and 60% boys strongly agreed that they would participate in acceptance activities in the future. While 16% girls and 12% boys respond somewhat, indicating partial agreement with the statement. In addition, 12% girls and 24% boys respond neutral, meaning they partially agree with the statement. A small proportion of 4% girls partially disagree about participating in activities, while 4% boys reported that they would never participate in such activities.

Fig. 1: Percentage distribution of feedback responses for acceptance skill activities

Table 2: Responses of Girls and Boys to the Most Preferred Acceptance Activities

Name of activity	Girls	Boys
Puzzle pieces of our	32	20
Self esteem dice	32	28
My heart map	36	44
Gratitude shield	0	8

In table 2, of all the activities, 44% of boys and 36% of girls preferred “My Heart Map”. This implies that individuals have an emotional connection to the activity since it provides them with a creative outlet for expressing their feelings, thoughts, and most importantly, their inner selves. “Puzzle Pieces of Our” and the “Self-esteem dice” were equally popular among 32% of girls each, whereas 20% boys liked the “Puzzle Pieces of Our” activity. The “self-esteem dice” was ranked as the second favourite by 28% of boys, suggesting that they were drawn to games and interactive activities. Gratitude Shield was totally disliked by girls (0%), and it was the least popular among boys (8%).

Fig. 2: Percentage distribution of responses of girls and boys for the most liked activity

Questions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
activities were engaging and interesting	Girls	25	3.68	0.48	48	0.0000	1.0000 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.68	0.63			
activities helped in acceptance	Girls	25	3.60	0.76	48	1.5951	0.1172 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.24	0.83			
activities enhance creativity	Girls	25	3.76	0.52	48	1.8116	0.0763 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.44	0.71			
wanted to participate in the future	Girls	25	3.48	0.87	48	0.8593	0.3944 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.24	1.09			

Table 3: t-Test comparison of mean scores of girls and boys on acceptance skill activities

Table 3 explains the findings of the acceptance activities. When it came to activities that were interesting and engaging, both groups reported the same mean scores ($M = 3.68$; $p = 1.000$). Activities that promoted acceptance (girls $M = 3.60$ vs. boys $M = 3.24$) and fostered creativity (girls $M = 3.76$ vs. boys $M = 3.44$) were scored slightly higher by girls than by boys. The willingness of girls to engage in future activities was also slightly higher (girls $M = 3.48$ vs. boys $M = 3.24$). In general, both boys and girls had a positive and nearly comparable opinion of the acceptance activities. There was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between boys and girls in the assessment of feedback on acceptance skill activities.

Table 4: Responses of the feedback form of Empathy Skill Activities

Questions	Gender	Level of response				
		Yes, very much	Somewhat	Neutral	Not really	Not, at all
engaging and interesting	Girls	92	8	0	0	0
	Boys	84	4	12	0	0
understanding others' perspectives & feelings	Girls	64	28	8	0	0
	Boys	52	24	24	0	0
activities helped in developing empathy	Girls	60	20	20	0	0
	Boys	44	24	32	0	0
helped in developing interpersonal relationships	Girls	80	12	4	4	0
	Boys	48	36	16	0	0
like to participate in activities in the future	Girls	80	4	12	0	4
	Boys	60	16	24	0	0

According to table 4, for the item “engaging and interesting”, 92% girls and 84% boys fully agreed that empathy skill activities were interesting and engaging. Additionally, 8% girls and 4% boys partially agree with the statement, while 12% boys provided a neutral response, indicating neither agree nor disagree.

For the statement “understanding others’ perspectives & feelings”, 64% girls and 52% boys strongly agreed that the empathy skill activities helped them in understanding others’ perspectives and feelings. Furthermore, 28% girls and 24% boys somewhat agreed, which

indicates a moderate level of agreement. While 8% girls and 24% boys provided a neutral response, indicating neither agree nor disagree.

Regarding the statement that “activities helped in developing empathy”, 60% girls and 44% boys strongly agree with the statement that the empathy skill activities helped them in developing empathy. While 20% girls and 24% boys somewhat agreed, which indicates a moderate level of agreement. While 20% girls and 32% boys respond neutral, that indicates neither agree nor disagree.

For the item that “helped in developing interpersonal relationships”, 80% girls and 48% boys strongly agree with the statement and feel that the empathy skill activities helped them in developing interpersonal relationships. And 12% girls and 36% boys partially agree. While 4% girls and 16% boys respond neutral, indicating neither agree nor disagree. But 4% girls partially disagreed about the statement of developing interpersonal relationships.

Finally, for the statement “willingness to participate in activities in the future”, 80% girls and 60% boys strongly agreed that they will participate in empathy activities in the future. While 4% girls and 16% boys respond somewhat, it indicates that they partially agree with the statement. 12% girls and 24% boys remain neutral, but 4% of girls responded that they would never participate in such activities.

Fig. 3: Percentage distribution of feedback responses for empathy skill activities

Table 5: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of empathy skill

Name of activity	Girls	Boys
Role play	16	16
Story making	60	72
Feeling detective	20	8
Treat others the way you like	4	4

According to Table 5, the most popular activity was "story making" according to 72% of boys and 60% of girls. The fact that both groups (16% girls and 16% boys) thought role play was an

equally fun activity shows how well-rounded its appeal is in encouraging empathy and active participation. "The Feeling Detective" activity was chosen by 20% girls and only 8% boys, a noticeable gender difference was seen in this. It suggests that girls were more engaged in activities that dealt with emotions and the recognition of feelings. Additionally, the "Treat Others the Way You Like" activity was chosen as the least preferred activity by 4% of girls and 4% of boys. Adolescents may not have been as interested in this activity as they were in other activities, based on the low liking.

Fig. 4: Percentage distribution of responses of girls and boys for the most liked activity

Table 6: t-Test comparison of mean scores of girls and boys on empathy skill activities

Questions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
activities are engaging and interesting	Girls	25	3.92	0.28	48	1.3650	0.1786 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.72	0.68			
understand others' perspectives & feelings	Girls	25	3.56	0.65	48	1.3151	0.1947 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.28	0.84			
activities helped in developing empathy	Girls	25	3.40	0.82	48	0.9886	0.3278 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.16	0.90			
helped in developing interpersonal relationships	Girls	25	3.68	0.75	48	1.7008	0.0954 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.32	0.75			
wanted to participate in the future	Girls	25	3.56	1.00	48	0.7566	0.4530 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.36	0.86			

Table 6 shows that both boys and girls found the activities interesting and engaging girls assessed them as slightly more ($M = 3.92$) than boys ($M = 3.72$). Girls also scored better in understanding others' perspectives & feelings ($M = 3.56$ vs. boys $M = 3.28$) and developing empathy (girls $M = 3.40$ vs. boys $M = 3.16$). In the same manner, girls felt that their interpersonal interactions had improved more ($M = 3.68$ vs. 3.32), and the result was close to significant ($p = 0.095$), indicating a potential trend. Both groups showed similar levels of willingness to engage in future activities, with females ($M = 3.56$) being marginally more willing than boys ($M = 3.36$). In general, both sexes had a favourable opinion of the empathy activities. There were no significant gender differences in any of the empathy skill activities examined.

Table 7: Responses of the feedback form of Decision-Making Skill activities

Questions	Gender	Level of response				
		Yes, very much	Somewhat	Neutral	Not really	Not, at all
engaging and interesting	Girls	84	12	0	0	4
	Boys	80	16	4	0	0
understand the steps of taking a good decision	Girls	68	20	12	0	0
	Boys	56	16	24	4	0
improved the ability to consider pros and cons before deciding	Girls	60	20	16	4	0
	Boys	52	16	14	4	0
activities helped develop decision-making skills	Girls	60	20	12	8	0
	Boys	52	12	28	8	0
like to participate in activities in the future	Girls	84	16	0	0	0
	Boys	76	16	8	0	0

Table 7 concluded that, in the statement “engaging and interesting”, 84% girls and 80% boys strongly agree that the decision-making skill activities were interesting and engaging. Furthermore, 12% girls and 16% boys partially agree with the statement, while 4% boys were neutral. But 4% of girls totally disagree with the statement.

For the statement that they “understand the steps of taking a good decision”, 68% girls and 56% boys strongly agreed that decision-making skill activities helped them in understanding

the steps of making good decisions. Additionally, 20% girls and 16% boys partially agree with the statement, while 12% girls and 24% boys were neutral. But 4% of boys partially disagreed about the statement.

In the statement, “improved the ability to consider pros and cons before deciding”, 60% girls and 52% boys strongly agreed that decision-making skill activities improve their ability to think about the pros and cons of problems before making a decision. And 20% girls and 16% boys partially agree with the statement, and 16% girls and 14% boys were neutral, while 4% girls and 4% boys partially disagreed about the statement.

Regarding the statement that “activities helped in developing decision-making skills”, 60% girls and 52% boys highly think that decision-making skill activities helped them in developing decision-making skills. And 20% girls and 12% boys partially agree with the statement, and 12% girls and 28% boys were neutral, indicating neither agree nor disagree, while 8% girls and 8% boys partially disagreed about the statement.

Finally, in a statement of willingness “to participate in these activities in the future”, 84% girls and 76% boys strongly agreed that they would participate in decision-making activities in the future. While 16% girls and 16% boys respond somewhat, it means they partially agree with the statement. But 8% of boys are neutral, which indicates neither agree nor disagree.

Fig. 5: Percentage distribution of feedback responses for decision-making skill activities

Table 8: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of decision-making skill

Name of activity	Girls	Boys
Marshmallow Spaghetti Tower	32	24
Card Tower	48	32
Decision-making wheel	16	20
Tic Tac Toe	4	24

Table 8 shows that 48% girls and 32% boys selected “Card Tower” as their favorite activity, making it the most popular overall. This indicates that structured and hands-on activities were highly attractive to both groups, particularly the girls. Furthermore, the “Marshmallow Spaghetti Tower” was chosen by girls (32%) over boys (24%), suggesting a greater interest in creative and useful activities. The fact that 20% boys preferred the Decision-Making Wheel

somewhat more than girls (16%) demonstrated their preferences for strategy-based assignments. 24% boys selected the “Tic Tac Toe” activity as their top selection, while only 4% girls did so. This implies that boys found the “Tic Tac Toe” activity more interesting or effective.

Fig. 6: Percentage distribution of responses of girls and boys for the most liked activity

Table 9: t-Test comparison of mean scores of girls and boys on decision-making skill activities

Questions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
activities were engaging and interesting	Girls	25	3.72	0.84	48	0.2017	0.8410 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.76	0.52			
understand the steps of making a good decision	Girls	25	3.56	0.71	48	1.3303	0.1897 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.24	0.97			
improved your ability to consider pros and cons before deciding	Girls	25	3.36	0.91	48	0.7460	0.4593 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.16	0.99			
develop decision making skills	Girls	25	3.32	0.99	48	0.8209	0.4157 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.08	1.08			
like to participate in these activities in the future	Girls	25	3.84	0.37	48	1.0954	0.2788 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.68	0.63			

Table 9 shows that, there were no statistically significant differences between the responses of boys and girls regarding decision-making activities on any of the items ($p > 0.05$). With nearly identical mean scores (Girls: $M = 3.72$, Boys: $M = 3.76$), both groups thought the activities

were interesting and engaging, suggesting that they enjoyed the sessions equally. Girls (M = 3.56) scored somewhat higher than boys (M = 3.24) on the item they understood the steps of taking a good decision. Similarly, compared to males (M = 3.16), girls (M = 3.36) reported an improvement in their capacity to weigh the pros and cons before making a decision. Girls (M = 3.32) also scored somewhat higher than boys (M = 3.08) in developing general decision-making skills. Lastly, both groups showed a favorable readiness to engage in comparable activities in the future, with girls (M = 3.84) somewhat higher than boys (M = 3.68).

Table 10: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of the Effective Communication skill

Questions	Gender	Level of response				
		Yes, very much	Somewhat	Neutral	Not really	Not, at all
engaging and interesting	Girls	84	16	0	0	0
	Boys	88	12	0	0	0
activities helped in developing effective communication skills	Girls	68	24	8	0	0
	Boys	60	20	16	4	0
feel confident in sharing thoughts with the group members	Girls	76	12	8	4	0
	Boys	56	12	8	4	0
learn teamwork from these activities	Girls	80	12	4	4	0
	Boys	76	20	4	0	0
like to participate in these activities in the future	Girls	68	28	0	4	0
	Boys	64	32	4	0	0

In the table 10, in statement “engaging and interesting” activities of developing effective communication were found engaging and interesting by 84% girls and 88% boys. While 16% girls and 12% boys were partially agreed with the statement.

For the statement, activities “helped in developing effective communication skills”, 68% girls and 60% boys fully agreed with the statement, but 24% girls and 20% boys partially agreed. And 8% girls and 16% boys were neutral for the statement, while 4% boys partially disagreed with the statement.

In the statement, “feel confident in sharing thoughts with the group members”, 76% girls and 56% boys responded strongly agree with the statement, 12% girls and boys each partially agree with the statement, 8% of girls and boys each remain neutral, and 4% of girls and boys each partially agree with the statement.

When it came to “learn teamwork from effective communication activities” statement, 80% girls and 76% boys fully agree with the statement, whereas 12% girls and 20% boys were partially agree with the statement, but 4% girls and boys each remain neutral, and 4% girls partially disagree.

Finally, in a statement of willingness “to participate in these activities in the future”, 68% girls and 64% boys strongly agreed that they would participate in effective communication activities in the future. While 28% girls and 32% boys respond somewhat, it means they partially agree with the statement. But 8% of boys are neutral, which indicates neither agree nor disagree, and 4% respond not really, which indicates partially disagree with the statement.

Fig. 7: Percentage distribution of feedback responses for effective communication skill activities

Table 11: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of effective communication skills

Name of activity	Girls	Boys
Dumb Charade	20	24
Broken Telephone	16	12
Stand up for fillers	32	20
Blindfold Activity	32	44

Table 11 concluded that, both girls and boys displayed a range of preferences when asked which activities they enjoyed the most. “Dumb Charade” was preferred by boys (24%) more than girls (20%). This suggests that boys enjoyed the challenge of performing and guessing better. Girls (16%) expressed a somewhat higher preference for “Broken Telephone” than did

boys (12%), suggesting that this communication-based game was more interesting to them overall. However, females (32%) preferred “Stand up for Fillers” more than boys (20%), indicating that girls found this interactive and self-esteem-boosting game more interesting. It's interesting to note that the “Blindfold Activity” was the most well-liked by both groups; boys (44%) exhibited a greater propensity than girls (32%), indicating a greater interest in experiential and trust-based activities. Overall, the data indicate that although both sexes liked a range of activities, males tended towards more playful and experiential activities, while girls favored more expressive and participative jobs.

Fig. 8: Percentage distribution of responses of girls and boys for the most liked activity

Table 12: t-Test comparison of mean scores of girls and boys on effective communication skill activities

Activities	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
engaging and interesting	Girls	25	3.84	0.37	48	0.4	0.6909 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.88	0.33			
activities helped in developing effective communication skills	Girls	25	3.60	0.65	48	1.0776	0.2866 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.36	0.91			
feel confident in sharing thoughts with the group members	Girls	25	3.36	0.91	48	0.7460	0.4593 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.16	0.99			
learn teamwork from the activities	Girls	25	3.68	0.75	48	0.2165	0.8295 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.72	0.54			
like to participate in these activities in the future	Girls	25	3.60	0.71	48	0.000	1.000 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.60	0.58			

Table 12 shows that, there were no significant differences between boys and girls in any of the items evaluated by the unpaired t-test for effective communication activities. The activities were deemed similarly fascinating and engaging by both groups: boys (M = 3.88) and girls (M = 3.84). When asked, the activities helped in the development of good communication skills; girls (M = 3.60) gave slightly higher ratings than boys (M = 3.36). Once more, girls (M = 3.36) had somewhat higher scores than boys (M = 3.16) in terms of confidence in sharing opinions and thoughts with group members. Boys (M = 3.72) scored higher than girls (M = 3.68) on the learn teamwork through activities. Lastly, with identical mean scores (boys: M = 3.60, girls: M = 3.60), both groups indicated an equal readiness to engage in such activities in the future.

Table 13: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of the Self Awareness skill

Questions	Gender	Level of response				
		Yes, very much	Somewhat	Neutral	Not really	Not, at all
engaging and interesting	Girls	76	24	0	0	0
	Boys	76	20	4	0	0
feel comfortable in accepting strength as well as weakness	Girls	84	12	4	0	0
	Boys	92	4	0	4	0
activities helped in identify those areas that can be improve	Girls	76	20	4	0	0
	Boys	84	12	0	4	0
activities helps in developing self awareness skills	Girls	72	20	8	0	0
	Boys	84	12	4	0	0
like to participate in these activities in the future	Girls	72	28	0	0	0
	Boys	80	16	4	0	0

Table 13 shows that, the statement, “engaging and interesting activities”, was highly enjoyable for both boys and girls. 76% girls responded “Yes, very much,” which shows they agreed with the statement, but 24% girls responded somewhat, which indicates they partially agree with the statement. And the boys did the same (76% responded “Yes, very much” and 20% “Somewhat”), with only 4% remaining neutral with the statement.

The majority of girls (84%) and boys (92%) strongly agreed with the “felt comfortable recognizing both strengths and limitations” statement. A small number of girls (12%) and boys (4%) chose "Somewhat", but 4% girls were neutral about the statement, and only 4% boys chose "Not really."

In the same way, the majority of girls (76%) and boys (84%) responded positively to “activities helped in identify the areas for improvement”, although 20% girls and 12% boys responded with a somewhat. 4% girls remain neutral, but 4% boys exhibited less belief.

Strong agreement was once again seen on the assertion that these activities helped in the development of self-awareness skills, with 72% girls and 84% boys choosing "Yes, very much," but 20% girls and 12% boys selected ‘somewhat, ’ which indicates partial agreement with the statement. Whereas 8% girls and 4% boys selected "Neutral".

Lastly, the majority of respondents expressed a strong desire to “engage in such activities in the future”, with 72% girls and 80% boys selecting "Yes, very much," 28 girls and 16 boys selecting "Somewhat," and just 4 boys selecting "Neutral."

Fig. 9: Percentage distribution of feedback responses for self-awareness skill activities

Table 14: Responses of girls and boys to the most preferred activity of the self-awareness skill

Name of activity	Girls	Boys
My strength and my weakness	48	28
Know Yourself	28	44
Boosting Self-Esteem	12	20
The 360-degree feedback	12	8

According to Table 14, girls preferred the “My Strength and My Weakness” activity the most (48% girls compared to 28% boys), indicating that they found self-reflective activities enjoyable. However, boys were more interested in structured self-exploration activity and preferred “Know Yourself” (44% boys compared to 28% girls). 20% boys prioritized “Boosting Self-Esteem” activity, indicating that boys prioritized activities that increased their self-confidence, and only 12% girls liked it. Feedback-based activities were not as engaging for both groups, as evidenced by the fact that only 12% girls and 8% boys chose the “360-Degree Feedback” activity.

Fig. 10: Percentage distribution of responses of girls and boys for the most liked activity

Table 15: t-Test comparison of mean scores of girls and boys on self-awareness skill activities

Questions	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
engaging and interesting	Girls	25	3.76	0.44	4 8	0.2877	0.7748 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.72	0.54			
feel comfortable in accepting your strength as well as your weakness	Girls	25	3.80	0.50	4 8	0.2500	0.8037 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.84	0.62			
activities helped you to identify those areas that you can improve	Girls	25	3.72	0.54	4 8	0.2335	0.8163 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.76	0.66			
these activities help you in developing self-awareness skills	Girls	25	3.64	0.64	4 8	0.9872	0.3285 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.80	0.50			
like to participate in these activities in the future	Girls	25	3.72	0.46	4 8	0.2877	0.7748 (non-significant)
	Boys	25	3.76	0.52			

Table 15 stated that the activities were seen as “interesting and engaging” by both groups: boys (M = 3.72) and girls (M = 3.76). Boys (M = 3.84) ranked somewhat higher than girls (M = 3.80) in the statement of “feeling comfortable accepting strengths and weaknesses”. Girls (M = 3.72) and boys (M = 3.76) gave nearly identical scores when asked if the activities “helped them identify areas of improvement”. Boys stated that these activities helped them in the “development of self-awareness skills” at somewhat higher ratings (M = 3.80) than girls (M = 3.64). Lastly, when asked about “future participation”, both groups showed interest, with boys (M = 3.76) and girls (M = 3.72). An independent sample t-test revealed that girls and boys rated the self-awareness activities similarly, with no statistically significant difference.

Discussion:

Findings of this study reveal that the intervention program successfully develops resilience in adolescents. According to the feedback form, the majority of both boys and girls responded that the activities on acceptance, empathy, decision-making, communication, and self-awareness were engaging, interesting, and beneficial, with no significant gender differences.

Teamwork and self-awareness were slightly greater for boys, while empathy and communication were slightly higher for girls. With these variations, the program successfully benefits both genders equally, as evidenced by the identical mean scores and the absence of significant p-values. This suggests that all participants, regardless of gender, benefit from the intervention’s successful advancement. Girls’ tendency to report better interpersonal interactions ($p = 0.095$) raises the possibility of minor gender effects that deserve more research. Furthermore, both groups showed a strong desire to attend future events, highlighting the program's accessibility and possibility of lasting impact.

The first objective of the study was to build resilience through an intervention program, and these results clearly address that objective. The constant positive feedback from all activities demonstrates that structured, activity-based therapies can successfully improve resilience. Likewise, the independent t-test was used to satisfy the second goal, which was to compare the resilience levels of boys and girls. The lack of significant gender differences indicates that the program was equally advantageous for both groups, underscoring its effectiveness and inclusion.

Overall, these findings confirm the intervention's applicability across a range of adolescent groups by demonstrating its effectiveness in fostering important social-emotional abilities in a gender-inclusive manner.

Conclusion:

The results of this study demonstrate that the intervention activities successfully involved both boys and girls and developed critical social and emotional competencies without any significant gender differences. The intervention program's inclusion and broad popularity are highlighted by the favorable and similar responses from both groups.

All things considered, the intervention effectively involves both sexes, fosters the development of skills, and motivates willingness to continue, providing a solid basis for the comprehensive development of adolescents. Future studies should look into long-term effects and subtle gender-specific experiences in order to maximize these interventions even further.

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Limitations:

The results of this study may not be as generalizable as they may be due to the relatively small sample size (N = 50) and the use of a self-constructed feedback instrument. To evaluate the long-term effects of interventions, future studies should use longitudinal designs, standardized resilience measures, and larger, multi-site samples. Furthermore, using metrics of particular adversities (such as socioeconomic difficulties or academic pressure) may help to shed light on how resilience abilities protect adolescents from outside pressures.

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